

Seasonal asymmetries and long-term trends in atmospheric and ionospheric temperatures in polar regions: an update (SATS 23)

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1. Introduction

During the last decades, temperatures in Arctic regions have increased much faster than the rest of the world (e.g. Rantanen et al. 2022). Svalbard, with its comprehensive infrastructure and availability of long-time measurement series is an ideal place to observe and investigate potential processes responsible for these changes. With this in mind, a cross-disciplinary group of researchers initiated a project, "Seasonal asymmetries and long-term trends in atmospheric and ionospheric temperatures in polar regions and their dependence on solar activity (SATS)", to study these processes. Initial results from this study were presented in the

SIOS 2022 report (Haaland et al. 2023, hereafter referred to as SATS).

This brief report updates the original SATS report, and we address some of the open issues and recommendations from the initial report. In addition to incremental updates of the existing data sets, we have added data sets describing the sea surface temperatures around Svalbard as well as a proxy for the global atmospheric CO₂ content. We also present some initial results, and provide an outlook for the use of machine learning to investigate large data sets.

2. The state of temperature trends in Svalbard

As in SATS, the aim of this study is to characterize long term trends in temperatures at and around Svalbard, and their response to external inputs such as atmospheric and ionospheric conditions and solar activity. The latter is of relevance since Svalbard possesses strong seasonal variations, is located in the geomagnetic cusp region (see e.g. Fritz and Fung 2005), and thus is more exposed to effects of the solar wind than lower latitudes. To perform such a characterization, we employ observations from a number of ground temperature stations, combine them with measurements and proxies for potential input parameters including atmospheric and ionospheric temperatures, sea temperatures, and solar activity, and use this data set as input to a model. Correlations between observations, as well as potential cause–effect links are discussed.

2.1. Overview of observations

Figure 1 shows the location of observatories used in the present study. In this update, we have extended data sets with another year of data, and investigated sea surface temperatures near Svalbard and their potential impact on ground temperatures. To get the global context, time series

of atmospheric CO₂ content have also been added to the data set. Below, we briefly introduce the new data sets and data handling. Due to limited space, we refer to the original SATS report and the cited references for more details about individual data sets.

2.1.1. Ground temperatures

In contrast to SATS, published last year, temperatures from the 6 ground stations are now combined into a single time series – *median ground temperature* (MGT). It contains the median of the different stations' temperature measurements for any time with at least four operative stations. We use this parameter to represent an average Svalbard temperature.

2.1.2. Sea surface temperatures

The Operational Sea Surface Temperature and Ice Analysis (OSTIA) cooperation generates high resolution sea surface temperature maps of the global ocean from satellite and in situ data (Donlon et al. 2012). OSTIA's satellite data come from infrared and microwave instruments on satellites, while in situ data (primarily used for calibration) are

Figure 1: Observatories used in this study. Red dots show ground temperature observatories, the blue dot indicates a mooring and the green dot indicates the position of the EISCAT radar system. The Mesospheric radar station is located near EISCAT. Sea surface temperatures used for the model are spatial averages from four different areas: North Svalbard (NS), Barents Sea (BS), South Cape (SC) and the West Spitsbergen Shelf (WSS). The colour-coded cloud around Ny-Ålesund indicates density of balloon observations as they drift in the wind after release, with yellow indicating dense observation frequency, blue indicating fewer observations. See Table 1 for observation periods and observatory coordinates.

from ships and buoys (Good et al. 2020). We have used spatially averaged data from 4 representative regions (Fig. 1) around Svalbard as proxies for the sea surface temperature.

2.1.3. Global atmospheric CO₂ content

Carbon dioxide (CO₂) is a greenhouse gas, i.e., it absorbs significantly more heat than the atmosphere's main natural constituents (nitrogen

and oxygen), and releases parts of the stored heat back to the atmosphere. An increase in atmospheric CO₂ is therefore linked to global warming. Local CO₂ measurements series are available from Ny-Ålesund (Platt et al. 2022), but as our aim is to set the observations into a global context, we source global CO₂ data from the Mauna Loa Volcanic Observatory in Hawaii (NOAA, 2023).

2.2. Methodology: Detrending seasonally varying data

Our focus is on *long term trends* in Svalbard temperatures. However, many of the observed parameters have strong seasonal variations governed by changing solar illumination as Earth rotates and orbits the Sun (effects of diurnal variations are filtered out by using the daily averages of the parameters). To filter out seasonal variations, we *detrend* the data as described in SATS. Basically, we fit the time series to a sinusoidal model representing season as shown in Equation (1), and extract three different key parameters from each measurement time series. The fit in this updated study is done over the years 2011-2018.

$$T(t, \alpha, C, \phi) = \alpha \sin\left(\frac{t+\phi}{365.242}\right) + C \quad (1)$$

Amplitude (α) can be interpreted as the difference between minimum and maximum temperatures. A decrease in amplitude over years would indicate less pronounced seasons. **Offset (C)** can be interpreted as a yearly average. An increase in offset over the years can be interpreted as a warming trend. **Phase shift (ϕ)** can be interpreted as the seasonal asymmetry. Due to heat storage capacity in the sea, ice and land, the highest temperatures do not occur at maximum solar illumination at midsummer, but are typically shifted towards autumn.

3. Results

3.1. Temperature characteristics

The results on trends and average profiles of amplitude, offset and phase shift of the temperature curves are not substantially altered by the inclusion of one additional year of data. The top part of Figure 2 is an update of Figure 5 included in last year's report (Haaland et al., 2023), but now augmented by 4 sea surface temperatures as described in section 2.1.

For the sea surface temperatures, indicated by coloured triangles in Figure 2, several features should be pointed out. The Barents Sea (BS) temperature has a lower average amplitude and a considerably larger average phase shift than the other regions investigated. This region has the lowest average sea surface temperature (see Table 1). A larger phase shift is also seen for the North Svalbard (NS) region. These two regions are typically covered by ice parts of the year. The behaviour can thus at least partly be explained by the higher heat capacity in the surrounding ice, associated feedback loops, and consequently longer response times to seasonal changes (Onarheim et al. 2018). Furthermore, the West Spitzbergen Shelf (WSS) and South Cape (SC) regions are strongly correlated

with each other. This correlation is primarily a result of heat transport by sea currents (e.g. Nilsen et al. 2016).

Figure 2d shows linear correlations between the different time series in the form of a colour coded correlation matrix. The brief update precludes a comprehensive discussion of all features, but we have labelled a few regions of particular interest in the correlation matrix. Label 1 highlights the strong correlation between sea surface temperatures in the WSS and SC regions, which can be attributed to sea currents. Label 2 highlights the difference in behaviour between the sea surface temperatures in the sometimes ice-covered BS region and the SC region, which is ice-free year-round. The difference in behaviour of these regions is most pronounced in the phase shift.

This correlation matrix also highlights some interesting features in the atmosphere. The 300 hPa size bin serves as a boundary (i.e., the tropopause) between the high-altitude, stratospheric region (pressure levels 0 to 200 hPa - label 3), and the tropospheric pressure levels at lower altitudes (label 4). This clear distinction between these regions is apparent in both amplitude, offset and phase shift.

4. New possibilities with machine learning

The large amount of data and the complex interactions between the regions studied led us to investigate alternative data processing methods. Machine learning methods lend themselves well to large datasets. For studying long-term trends in the temperature, the use of regression supervised learning is of particular relevance (e.g. Rolnick et al. 2022). Supervised learning has the ability to learn mappings between inputs and outputs in a continuous numerical form due to its regression (in data science, inputs to a model are often referred to as *features*, and outputs are referred to as *targets*).

4.1. Choice of model: Multi-Variate Linear Regression

This brief update of SATS does not allow an elaborate explanation of the various machine learning methods, or exploration of all aspects of our large data set. However, as a proof of concept, the simplest supervised learning regressor model, the Multi-Variate Linear Regression (MVLRL) model, was tested for this update. The aim was to predict ground temperatures (targets) based on input parameters such as solar energy influx and temperatures in the upper atmosphere (features).

Average Fit Parameters

Figure 3: Fit parameters (amplitude, offset and phase shift) based on measurements in blue, and the same parameters predicted from the MVLR model outputs in red.

Due to its linear structure it is easy to determine feature importance, and its simplicity makes MVLR a versatile model that can be applied to many different problems. MVLR also has downsides that are not easily overcome, such as its tendency to over-fit when a large number of (partially correlated) input features are used. Moreover, outliers in the data set can significantly influence model output, and a good fit on the data does not necessarily imply causality. Still, the model gives further insight in the data set, and allows for predictions of the output targets.

4.2. Predictions from the MVLR model

Although multi-label regression models and classifiers capable of predicting several targets exist, we chose the simplest possible approach: 3 separate MVLR models are set up, each predicting one of the 3 targets: median ground-station temperature (MGT) amplitude [°C], offset [°C], and phase shift [days], respectively. For this

proof of concept, 27 input parameters based on data collected at high altitudes (>700 hPa isobar, corresponding to ~3 km or more above sea level) and 5 global parameters (global atmospheric CO_2 concentration, the $F_{10.7}$ solar activity index, the DST magnetic disturbances index, the solar energy influx P_{in} , and the average Svalbard sun hours) are used as input features to the 3 models. Input features are indicated in bold black text, and targets in red bold text in Figure 2.

We used a 3:1 train/test ratio for the model. That is, the MVLR model is trained on the first 75% of the data set (years 2003-2016; days with data gaps have been removed). The last 25% (from late 2016 to 2021) are predicted. Figure 3 shows the result of this fit, in the form of detrended fit parameters (amplitude, offset and phase shift) in blue, and MVLR model outputs of the same parameters in red. The figure demonstrates that the MVLR model can reasonably predict the detrended fit parameters of the MGT by using features that are normally not considered to have a strong linear correlation on

Figure 2: Profiles of the sine wave parameters fitted to the temperature measurements (top) and correlations between modelling parameters (bottom). a): Amplitude (i.e., essentially difference between min and max temperatures). b): Offset (can be interpreted as yearly average temperature). c): Seasonal offset (i.e., phase shift between seasonal solar illumination and temperature). d): Colour-coded matrix showing correlations between parameters. Parameters printed in bold text at the edges are used in the machine learning model discussed in section 4. Red ellipses labelled (1) to (4) indicate key features discussed in the text on page 27.

their own as shown in Figure 2.

Although the model suffers from over-fitting the data, the introduction of global variables such as CO₂ reduces this over-fitting. This can largely be attributed to the introduction of significant long-term trends in the feature pool allowing the model

to reproduce and predict the observed trends in ground temperatures. Note that we did not try to optimize the model or choice of input features (e.g. Van Der Maaten et al. 2009) in this proof of concept. We expect to achieve even better prediction accuracy with other models and further optimizations.

5. Contributions to interdisciplinarity

In SATS, we studied long-term trends in temperatures around Svalbard from the sea to space. Here we have updated our existing dataset through summer 2023. We now also included ocean/sea surface measurements based on remote sensing by satellites. As in SATS, this update involves science disciplines from sea to space: oceanography, meteorology, atmospheric physics, ionospheric physics and space physics. Our data set is comprehensive and diverse (also see Table 1).

5.1. Main findings

The addition of a year of observations did not significantly alter the overall conclusions reported in SATS. Based on our new, updated data set, the following main findings still hold:

- Ground temperatures in Svalbard increase over time, and the difference between summer and winter temperatures decreases.
- The seasonal asymmetry increases; the day of the year with maximum ground temperature shifts toward autumn.
- Ground temperatures seem largely unaffected by solar activity; the last solar cycle is weaker in terms of electromagnetic energy transfer than previous solar cycles, but ground temperature trends still show an increase.
- Temperature trends in the lower atmosphere (below the tropopause) are similar to those for ground temperatures.

Sea surface temperatures around Svalbard show distinct differences between regions. In particular the BS and NS regions, which are partly covered by ice for periods, show less summer–winter variation, and a larger seasonal shift (longer response times). The other regions are connected by sea currents and show more similar behaviour.

Results from MVLR machine learning model reveal correlations between ground temperatures and the upper atmosphere, mesosphere as well as global proxies such as CO₂ content, geomagnetic activity and solar activity. Classical methods do not show any significant correlations between these parameters. The cause-effect link is not clear, though. It may be that ground (and sea surface) temperatures affect the upper atmosphere rather than vice versa. Still, machine learning can provide new insight and reveal new correlations, and will probably become more important for processing of large data sets in the future.

As demonstrated, machine learning can also be used to predict temperatures based on input parameters from other regions. Potential uses for machine learning could be to predict temperatures in places where no observations are available or possible, predict future trends and fill data gaps in observations.

6. Open questions and recommendations for the future

Several open questions remain. We still do not know what underlies the observed trends and changes. Are the changes primarily the result of global effects (cf. the greenhouse effect as discussed in IPCC (2023)), or can the observed trends primarily be attributed to local conditions? The impact of sea ice coverage and heat transport by sea currents is also still not fully understood. Another question is how and whether the observed trends will continue in the future. How do long-term cyclic effects, e.g., ice extent and ice cap motion, affect ground temperatures? Finally, what consequences will the observed trends have for society in Svalbard?

In this study, we barely touched upon possibilities with machine learning and data-driven models. One clear recommendation from this update is to further utilize such methods, and make use of cross disciplinary data sets as inputs to the models. New data-driven models and use of machine learning also allow larger data sets to be processed, and greater spatial and temporal variations to be assessed. So far we have not utilized local wind measurements or local solar radiance measurements (and these

do not exist for all stations), but these should be included where available.

For an arctic island archipelago like Svalbard, the interactions between sea, ice and land are of key importance for understanding the local climate. The location in the geomagnetic cusp region also means that solar activity and electromagnetic energy from solar wind have more direct impact, in particular in the upper atmosphere and ionosphere. Thus, the need for interdisciplinary investigations encompassing space/solar physics, meteorology, oceanography and glaciology cannot be emphasized enough.

Our final recommendation not only applies to science investigations, but also policy: decisions made to address challenges arising from the warming trend should be based on scientific data. Consequently, there is a need to maintain the existing observation grid, and to expand this to new regions (e.g., observations from Svalbard's interior regions remain few).

7. Data availability

All data used for this study are available from public archives. Links to data sources and an overview of

station coordinates for each dataset are shown in Table 1.

8. Acknowledgements

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Table 1: Updated list of data sets, observatories, their geographic location and elevation above mean sea level, time of operation, data availability as well as mean temperature over the given time interval.

Dataset	Station	Latitude	Longitude	Altitude	Period	Data points	T _{avg}	Dataset provider	Metadata access (URL)	Remarks
OSTIA SST	OSTIA Barents Sea	76.8-78.5	24.4-27.0	0m	2005-09-16 2021-10-08	15264	-1.7 °C	Copernicus Climate	https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00165	See "Data access and mapping services" in given URL.
	OSTIA North of Svalbard	80.5-82.7	17.0-19.0	0m	1981-10-01 2023-06-24	15252	-1.6 °C	Copernicus Climate	https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00165	
	OSTIA South Cape	75.0-76.3	16.5-18.5	0m	1981-10-01 2023-06-24	15242	2.5 °C	Copernicus Climate	https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00165	SATS contact person: Ragnheid Skogseth (ragnheids@unis.no)
	OSTIA West Spitsbergen	76.5-78.0	11.0-13.5	0m	1981-10-01 2023-06-24	15252	2.7 °C	Copernicus Climate	https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00165	
Isfjorden temperatures	Isfjord mouth	78.06	13.52	-150 - -200m	1981-10-01 2023-06-24	95969	3.0 °C	Norwegian Polar Institute	https://data.polar.no/dataset/42927488-f4e7-4470-b107-44c4f2bd0c36	Select station and time interval, thereafter "Mean air temperature (24h)" in given URL
	Ground temperatures	Hopen	76.51	25.01	6m	1970-01-01 2023-06-27	19517	-4.46 °C	Norwegian Centre for Climate Research	
	Ny-Ålesund	78.92	11.89	8m	1974-08-01 2023-06-27	17522	-4.69 °C	Norwegian Centre for Climate Research	https://www.seklima.net/no	SATS contact person: Antonia Radlwimmer (Quiv@web.de)
	Longyearbyen Airport	78.24	15.49	28m	1975-08-01 2023-06-27	17413	-4.59 °C	Norwegian Centre for Climate Research	https://www.seklima.net/no	
	Svea	77.89	17.72	9m	1978-05-01 2022-07-31	15508	-5.56 °C	Norwegian Centre for Climate Research	https://www.seklima.net/no	SATS contact person: Alfred Wegener Institute (AWI) and Norwegian Meteorological Institute
	Edgeøya (Kapp Heuglin)	78.25	22.81	14m	1992-09-03 2023-06-26	8670	-6.04 °C	Norwegian Centre for Climate Research	https://www.seklima.net/no	
	Karl XII øya	80.65	25.00	5m	2000-08-01 2023-05-10	5709	-6.77 °C	Norwegian Centre for Climate Research	https://www.seklima.net/no	SATS contact person: Brandon van Schaik (brandon.vanschalk@epfl.ch)
	Weather balloon	Atmosphere (balloon)	78.92	11.89	0-25km	1993-01-01 2023-07-03	ca 110000	(*)	Alfred Wegener Institute (AWI) and Norwegian Meteorological Institute	
Mesospheric radar	Mesosphere (radar)	78.17	16.00	ca 90km	2001-10-16 2023-07-31	7080	181.3 K	Tromsø Geophysical Observatory	https://www.tgo.uib.no/	
EISCAT	Eiscat Svalbard	78.09	16.03	>100km	1999-12-01 2021-03-23	4837	486.0 K	National Polar Institute, Japan	http://esr.nipr.ac.jp/www/eiscatdata/	
Global CO ₂ data	Mauna Loa, Hawaii	19.53	-155.58	3400m	1974-05-19 2023-07-16	15131	-	National Oceanographic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA)	https://gml.noaa.gov/ccgg/trends/data.html	
Solar wind and F10.7	Solar Measurement	(*)	(*)	(*)	1980-01-01 2023-08-01	14151	-	NASA CDWeb	https://cdweb.gsfc.nasa.gov/index.html	

(*) As in Haaland et al. 2023, we divide balloon measurements into 11 pressure altitude levels up to ca 25 km altitude. Each pressure level contains approximately 10000 averages, and overall average temperatures vary from -3.3°C near ground to -57.4°C in pressure level 0 (i.e., atmospheric pressure below 100 mBar, corresponding to altitudes above ca 15 km).

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